

CONTROVERSIAL ISSUES IN THE HANAFI AND SHAFI'I SECTS MENTIONED IN THE WORK "RUUSUL-MASAIL".

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Abstract. Maḥmūd Zamakhsharī is a great mufassir, mutakallim, jurist who came from Movarounnahr. When the scientific, cultural and economic situation in Mā Warā' al-Nahr was in decline, Maḥmūd Zamakhsharī served to revive and restore science with selfless scientists. Ten of his works are known today, and scientific researches on these works continue without stopping.

Key words: Nu'mān ibn Thābit, Maḥmūd Zamakhsharī, ibn Khallikān, Ḥājjī Khalīfah, Muḥammad ibn Idrīs ash-Shāfi'ī, Ru'ūs al-masā'il, Tāj al-tarājim, al-A'lām.

In the "Book of Guarantees" of "Ruusul-Masail" two issues are mentioned which are disputed in the Hanafi and Shafi'i madhhabs. Guarantee means "to add, to undertake" ¹. It means undertaking to make a payment in money or in person. In issue 205 of the book, Zamakhshari noted the following: "It is right for us to be a guarantor with one's body, not with wealth. Shofei said that it is invalid to be a guarantor with the body. Our evidence in this matter: before the guarantor judge, the claimant has assumed the right he is demanding. It is wajib to be a guarantor compared to being a surety"².

The approach of the Hanafi sect in this matter is aimed at justifying that the actions of guarantors who do not have money for others are mashru', i.e. legal. This approach is important in promoting people to help each other.

In the "Book of Companionship" of "Ruusul-Masail" 4 issues are mentioned that are controversial in the Hanafi and Shafi'i madhhabs. Partnership is expressed in the book by the word "company". The dictionary translation is "interference". In istilah: "One thing belongs to two or more people."

In issue 207 of the Book of Partnership, Zamakhshari noted the following: "Abdon partnership is permissible for us. According to Shofei, it is invalid. Abdon means two bodies. Another name for it is partnership in production, occupation and reception. Shirk al-abdon is a partnership in production, craft, profession. Commenting on this issue, Zamakhshari states the following: "Shirka al-abdan:

¹ Abul-barakot Abdulloh ibn Ahmad an-Nasafiy. Kanz ad-daqiq. –Madina: Dar as-siraj, 2011. -B.448

² Mahmud Zamaxshariy. "Ruus al-masail". Nashrga tayyorlovchi: Abdulloh Nazir Ahmad. –Bayrut: "Dar al-bashair al-islamiya", 1987. –B.322.

two people who are partners in professions and crafts and divide the profits that God has provided for them, is permissible for us, but not permissible according to Shafei. Our evidence in this matter: This form of partnership has become a custom and tradition among people. People's traditions have an influence on the meaning of being morally correct. Just like shirka al-inan"³. In Shirk al-inan, two people act in partnership with their property and labor and share the profit between them. In this case, the contribution of both parties is not necessarily equal, the contribution and profit are based on mutual agreement.

Shofei proves his point of view on this issue as follows: "One of the conditions for the partnership to be valid is the existence of a certain material value at the time of the partnership agreement, and the partnership is based on it. Here, a partnership is being made in a profession, a profession is something that does not have a material appearance and cannot be based on it when concluding a partnership agreement. Just like you can't share in chopping wood or mowing grass." One of the reasons why the teachings of the Hanafi sect are recognized as relatively moderate is that it pays attention to the customs and traditions of people. The issue mentioned above is a clear proof in this regard. The tradition of people is shown as proof of the permission of partnership in this profession.

In the "Book of Representation" of "Ruusul-Masail" 7 issues are mentioned that are disputed in the Hanafi and Shafi'i schools of thought ⁴. "Partnership" is expressed in the book by the word "wakola". The dictionary translation is: "to hand over and represent", in the translation: "One person transfers the power of ownership of something to another person."

In issue 214 of the Book of Representation, Zamakhshari noted the following: "It is correct for us to represent a minor (sabi), but it is not correct for Shofei." Our evidence in this matter is that if a child is sane, he can properly enter into a legal relationship. The reason is that he is not yet an adult, so that he cannot harm himself. Knowing that the child is a minor, this behavior of the person appointing him as a representative means that he agrees in advance to the possible harm from the child.

Shofei argued this issue as follows: "A child cannot own his property independently; how can he own another person's property ⁵". This issue proves

³ Chester Beatty Library. CBL AR 3600.-B.52.

⁴ Abdulhalim ibn Muhammad. Az-Zamaxshariyning Ruus al-masail asari ilmiy-tanqidiy matni. Sent-Endryus universiteti (Shotlandiya), 1977. –B.104.

⁵ Mahmud Zamaxshariy. "Ruus al-masail". Nashrga tayyorlovchi: Abdulloh Nazir Ahmad. –Bayrut: "Dar al-bashair al-Islamiya", 1987. –B.333.

that in the Hanafi madhhab, the rights and freedoms of not only adults, but also children are given a lot of attention.

In the "Book of Confessions" of "Ruusul-Masail" 5 issues are mentioned, which are controversial in the Hanafi and Shafi'i madhhabs. The dictionary meaning of "confession" is explained as "recognition, recognition". In istilah: "It is to inform that one has the right of another."⁶

In issue 218 of the Book of Confessions, Zamakhshari noted the following: "It is correct in our madhhab for a minor to confess (an obligation) with the permission of his guardian." Shofei said that it was incorrect. Our evidence in this matter: "Although a minor has the potential to own property, he is deprived of this right because he is underage and the ownership potential is not recognized in him. If the guardian allows the child, it means that he can have independent ownership. If possession is allowed, his confession must be correct. Because ownership is not correct without confession, its correctness is as important as a person in adulthood.

Shofei proved his point of view on this matter as follows: "A minor cannot claim ownership of his property without the permission of his guardian, because the child does not have the capacity, it is not right for him. The permission of the guardian does not create competence in the child"⁷.

The recognition of the opinion of a minor child regarding property rights is a clear proof that the Hanafi madhhab is recognized as a tolerant madhhab.

In the "Book of Oriat" of "Ruusul-Masail" 3 issues are mentioned, which are disputed in the Hanafi and Shafi'i madhhabs. The dictionary meaning of "Oriat" is interpreted as "coming and going". It means to use something. In Istilah, the Hanafis defined it as: "Owning irreplaceable interests."⁸ The Shafi'is defined it as: "Using something to the extent that it is possible to use it while preserving its essence."

In issue 224 of the Book of Oriat, Zamakhshari noted the following: "One who takes something as an oriat can give it to someone else as an oriat. It is not possible in the eyes of Shofei. Our proof in this matter is: "If the giver gives something to the Oriyat, he gives it absolutely. He agrees to use it. If a person acquires something, both he and others will use it. For this reason, it is obligatory for an ariat to own what he has received, just as if he was allowed to use it.

⁶ Abul-barakot Abdulloh ibn Ahmad an-Nasafiy. Kanz ad-daqoiq. –Madina: Dar as-siraj, 2011. -B.507

⁷ Chester Beatty Library. CBL AR 3600.-B.54.

⁸ Abul-barakot Abdulloh ibn Ahmad an-Nasafiy. Kanz ad-daqoiq. –Madina: Dar as-siraj, 2011. -B.534

Shofei gave the following evidence for his view on this issue: "People differ from each other in using things, especially in riding something. He agrees to ride and use anything other than an animal. It follows from this that the person receiving the ariat cannot give it to another person. It's similar to what we said about rent. It is not permissible for a person to rent a property from someone and give it to someone else to use, or to give his property to someone for safekeeping. Because a person who rents or takes possession cannot own this property. Same here⁹".

This issue proves that the Hanafi sect paid a lot of attention to human rights and freedom.

In the Book of Ghasb of Ruusul-Masail, 10 controversial issues are mentioned in the Hanafi and Shafi'i madhhabs. The dictionary meaning of "usurpation" is explained as "taking something by oppression and coercion". The Shafi'is defined it as: "Using the rights of others by violence."

In issue 228 of Ghasb Book, Zamakhshari noted the following: "If a Muslim spills the khamri (intoxicating drink) of a dhimmi, in our eyes, he will pay the price. It does not pay in the eyes of Shofei. Our evidence in this matter is that the dhimmi's liquor is like the Muslim's vinegar. If a Muslim spills a Muslim's vinegar, he pays the value of the dhimmi as well as the damage. Because the call in the Holy Qur'an about the prohibition of alcohol is specific to Muslims: "O you who believe! Indeed, may (intoxicating drinks), gambling, idolatry and (divining) sticks are impurities of the work of Satan, so avoid them! Perhaps (then) you will be saved" (Surat Ma'ida, 90)¹⁰. From this we know that the address in the verse is specific to a Muslim. As for the unbeliever, he remained honest.

Shofei proved his point of view as follows: "Khamr is not included in the series of wealth. He does not pay for the damage caused to him, just like if a Muslim breaks his heart, he does not pay for the damage. Our disagreement is about whether or not the admonition regarding prayers applies to the unbeliever. But there is no difference in the fact that the speech about forbidden things applies equally to the Muslim and the unbeliever. ¹¹"

It is known that Hanafism is recognized as a tolerant sect. The teaching of this sect is significant due to its attention to the rights of representatives of other

⁹ Abdulhalim ibn Muhammad. Az-Zamakhshariyning Ruus al-masail asari ilmiy-tanqidiy matni. Sent-Endryus universiteti (Shotlandiya), 1977. –B.228.

¹⁰ Qur'oni karim ma'nolarining tarjima va tafsiri. Tarjima va tafsir muallifi Shayx Abdulaziz Mansur. – Toshkent: Sano-standart,2021. –B.123

¹¹ Mahmud Zamakhshariy. "Ruus al-masail". Nashrga tayyorlovchi: Abdulloh Nazir Ahmad. –Bayrut: "Dar al-bashair al-Islamiya", 1987. –B.348.

religions and beliefs compared to other sects. If the property of a representative of a different religion is lost, approaching it not from the point of view of faith, but from the point of view of law shows the importance of the principle of humanitarianism in Hanafi.

In problem 230 of "Ghasb Kitobi" Zamakhshari noted the following: "If there is a bird belonging to a person in a cage or there is a chorpo in the pen, if he opens the door of the cage or pen, the bird flies and the chorpo leaves, our with us, there is no payment for it. According to Shofei, if it stays for an hour and then flies away, there is no payment for it¹²".

Our evidence in this matter is: "The animal's behavior is not remarkable. If an animal under human control causes a crime or damage, the owner shall pay for its damage. It is not a bird's verb to open the door here, and it flew away by itself, and now there is no payment for it. Just as if the shepherd is caught and the sheep perish, there is no ransom. It's the same here."

In this matter, Shofei proves the following hadith of the Prophet: "There is no payment for the actions of animals." If we accept that there is no payment for their behavior, then opening the door becomes a loss to the property and it is obligatory to pay for its damage. Just like their expulsion.

In this matter, the approach of the Hanafi sect is noteworthy in that it emphasizes that there is no penalty for unintentionally causing damage.

In the "Wadi'a book" of "Ruusul-Masail", 2 issues are mentioned, which are disputed in the Hanafi and Shafi'i madhhabs. The literal meaning of the word "Wadi'a" is "abandonment". In Istilah, the Hanafis defined it as: "Giving control to another person to protect one's property."¹³. The Shofeis defined it as "property handed over to a stranger for safekeeping." In issue 237 of the Book of Wadia, Zamakhshari noted the following: "If a child who does not have the capacity to deal is left with something to keep and loses it, it will not be considered a loss in our eyes. Shafei will be with him."

Our evidence in this matter is: "Whoever leaves something in front of a young child has condemned him to loss. Because it is a habit of children to eat the food placed in front of them, if there is something to ride, to ride it. So, the person who entrusts the thing to the child agrees to his loss. It is obligatory not to pay for the damage. It's like ordering damage to something¹⁴".

¹² Chester Beatty Library. CBL AR 3600.-B.58.

¹³ Abul-barakot Abdulloh ibn Ahmad an-Nasafiy. Kanz ad-daqiq. -Madina: Dar as-siraj, 2011. -B.531

¹⁴ Chester Beatty Library. CBL AR 3600.-B.61.

Shofei proves his point of view as follows: "The one who places a deposit in front of a child usually commands to keep it and does not command to destroy it. If a child causes damage, it is obligatory to pay for the damage. Because this payment is a payment for behavior. Children are not responsible for what they say, but they are responsible for their actions. Don't you see that if the child had caused damage to this thing before the deposit was handed over to him, he would have been compensated? It's the same here." This issue once again proves that the Hanafi madhhab focuses on ensuring the rights and freedoms of children.

Although "Ruusul-Masail" is considered an important work in the field of comparative jurisprudence, it was mainly used by jurists of the Hanafi sect. The persons who left their names at the beginning of the book are also jurists of the Hanafi school. This unique work of Zamakhshari has gained importance and fame in the foundation of the doctrine of the Hanafi sect over the centuries. In the 11th and 12th centuries, jurists of the Hanafi and Shafi'i schools worked in Khorezm and in the Movarounnahr area. It is in this period that the writing of "Ruusul-Masail" by Mahmud Zamakhshari, which expresses and protects the views of the Hanafi school to a certain extent, has a logical basis for the importance of Hanafi becoming the leading school in the region. Among Mahmud Zamakhshari's teachers and students, there are many jurists of the Hanafi school.

It is appropriate to present the following conclusions regarding Zamakhshari's approach to explaining the teachings of the Hanafi sect:

Mahmoud Zamakhshari had a good understanding of the doctrine of the Hanafi sect and was able to present the legal issues related to this doctrine in a reasonable manner in his works. Mahmoud Zamakhshari's views on the Hanafi school are consistent with the rulings of the famous Hanafi sources such as "Hidaya", "Kanz ad-Daqiq", "Tuhfa al-Fuqaho" and "Badayi' - as-sanayi".

Alloma showed the tolerant aspects of the teachings of the Hanafi sect in "Ruusu-Masail". In all matters of "Ruusual-Masail" he presented the teachings of the Hanafi sect through expressions such as "We" or "Our suggestion".

Zamakhshari's reasonable presentation of the teachings of the Hanafi madhhab in "Ruusul-Masail" confirms that he is a mature representative of this madhhab. Zamakhshari's approach to presenting the teachings of the Hanafi sect in "Ruusul-Masail" shows that he knows not only the doctrine of the sect, but also its sources

